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Review Article

IONTOPHORESIS USAGE IN DERMAL DELIVERY SYSTEMS**A.V.S.Madhulatha^{1*}, Ch.V.Suresh², D.Guruswamy³, G.Tejaswari³, M.Anil³,
M.Bogeswarreddy³**¹Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.²Principal, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601³Research Scholar, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.**Abstract:**

Iontophoresis is facilitated movement of ions across a membrane under the influence of an externally applied electric potential difference, is one of the most promising physical skin penetration enhancing method. Recently, there has been increased interest in using this technique for the transdermal delivery of medications, both ionic and nonionic. The rationale behind using this technique is the capability of this method to increase the systemic delivery of high molecular weight compounds with controlled input kinetics and minimum inter-subject variability, which is otherwise achieved only when parenteral route of administration is used. Mechanism of iontophoretic transport of drugs across the skin involves either diffusion, migration or electroosmosis. Various parameters which affect the transdermal absorption of drugs through iontophoresis like drug concentration, polarity of drugs, pH of donor solution, ionic strength, electrode polarity etc. have also been reviewed in detail. In therapeutic context, it is used to facilitate the administration of bioactive substances, either systemically or locally. The technique presents various advantages and that is why it has been successfully used by a plethora of medical sciences. The constantly developing field of dermato-cosmetic science has also taken advantage of the possibilities offered by iontophoresis, aiming to enhance the delivery of the applied active ingredients and, thus, induce the desired cosmetic effects. Iontophoresis can be safely and successfully used in the treatment of ageing, photoageing, hyperpigmentation, oxidative stress, hair loss, hair removal, acne, acne sequelae and cellulite, providing many possibilities for enhanced treatment results.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Transdermal drug delivery offers significant potential for the non-invasive administration of therapeutic agents. In addition to avoiding the hepatic first-pass effect and chemical degradation in the potentially hostile environment of the gastrointestinal tract, the skin provides a large, accessible surface area. The principle disadvantage is that the skin's homeostatic and protective functions have ensured that its outermost layer, the stratum corneum (SC), has evolved into a formidable barrier membrane [1]. In order to maintain homeostasis and regulate transepidermal water loss, the SC possesses a multilamellar lipidic structure punctuated by proteinaceous corneocytes that impose a significant tortuosity on the diffusion path across the membrane [2]. The architecture and composition of the SC have severely limited the number of molecules that can be delivered passively across the skin. The currently available transdermal drugs (clonidine, estradiol, fentanyl, nicotine, nitro-glycerine, scopolamine, testosterone, oxybutynin and the combination products norelgestromin/ethinyl estradiol and estradiol/norethindrone acetate) are all potent low molecular weight molecules which are active at blood

concentrations on the order of a few ng/ml or less [3]. In order to increase the range of drugs available for transdermal delivery a number of chemical and physical enhancement techniques have been developed in an attempt to compromise skin barrier function in a reversible manner without concomitant skin irritation. The controlled delivery afforded by constant current iontophoresis, which involves the application of a small electrical potential to maintain, as its name suggests, a constant current, sets it apart from other technologies. The amount of compound delivered is directly proportional to the quantity of charge passed; it depends on the applied current, the duration of current application and the area of the skin surface in contact with the active electrode compartment.

2. Iontophoretic electrochemistry

An iontophoretic device comprises a power source and two electrode compartments Fig. 1. The drug formulation (D+A₋) containing the ionized molecule (D⁺) is placed in the electrode compartment bearing the same charge; for example, a positively charged drug such as lidocaine would be placed in the anodal compartment. The indifferent electrode compartment

Fig. 1. Iontophoresis using a Ag/AgCl electrode system. The anodal compartment contains an ionizable drug D⁺ with its counter-ion A₋ and Na⁺Cl⁻. Application of an electric potential causes a current to flow through the circuit. At the electrode solution interface, the Ag⁺ and Cl⁻ react to form insoluble AgCl, which is deposited on the electrode surface. Electromigration transports the cations, including the drug molecule, from the anodal compartment and into the skin. At the same time, endogenous anions, primarily Cl⁻, move into the anodal compartment. In the cathodal chamber, Cl⁻ ions are released from the electrode and electroneutrality requires that either an anion is lost from the cathodal chamber or that a cation enters the chamber from the skin.

is placed at a distal site on the skin. Although there are many different types of electrode, the most well-suited to iontophoresis is the Ag/AgCl couple [4–6]. First, it avoids the sharp decreases in pH that are seen with, for example, Pt-metal electrodes: Ag/AgCl electrodes have the considerable advantage that their electrochemistry occurs at voltages lower than those necessary for the electrolysis of water, which is undesirable for two reasons: first, the protons created at the anode compete to carry charge and because of their small size and high mobility, they may significantly reduce drug delivery efficiency, and second, the low pH produced in the anodal compartment can lead to acid-induced skin burns and it may have an adverse effect on drug stability. Once the current is applied, the electric field imposes directionality on the movements of the ions present: positive charges in the anodal compartment move towards the cathode whereas anions move in the opposite direction.

The electrochemistry occurring at the Ag anode necessitates the presence of Cl⁻ ions in the anodal compartment: this requirement usually leads to a decrease in drug delivery efficiency since the NaCl commonly used to provide Cl⁻ also introduces significant concentrations of highly mobile Na⁺ ions which compete very effectively with the drug to carry current. As the Cl⁻ ions arrive at the electrode solution interface, they react with the metallic silver to form silver chloride, which on account of its low solubility product, is deposited at the electrode surface, simultaneously releasing an electron. In order to maintain electroneutrality in the anodal compartment, either a cation must move out of the compartment and into the skin or an anion must leave the skin and move into the anodal chamber. In the cathodal compartment, the AgCl is reduced by the arrival of electrons from the power supply and yields metallic silver together with a Cl⁻ ion, which passes into the solution. Again, for electroneutrality, this must be compensated for by the arrival of a cation from within the skin into the cathodal chamber or by the loss of an anion. Since the electrical circuit is completed by the endogenous inorganic ions that are present in the skin, primarily Na⁺ and Cl⁻, these latter species can impact on the efficiency of drug transport.

3. Iontophoretic transport mechanism (7)

Skin is known to consist of lipids (15-20%) (Triglycerides, free fatty acids, cholesterol, and phospholipids), 40% proteins (mostly keratin) and approximately 40% water. When applied across the skin, as in case of iontophoretic treatment, an

electric potential may alter the molecular arrangement of these components. This alteration could yield some change in the skin permeability. The flip-flop gating mechanism could be an operating model for the voltage dependent pore formation in the stratum corneum which is rich in keratin, an alpha-helical polypeptide. The flip-flop of polypeptide helices may occur to form a parallel arrangement. Pores are thus opened up as a result of the repulsion between neighbouring dipoles, and water molecules and ions will flow in the pore channel to neutralise the dipole moments. The phenomenon should lead to an enhancement in skin permeability for peptide and protein molecules, and other charged molecule.

The isoelectric point of the skin is between 3 and 4, that pores have a positive charge below pH 3 and a negative charge above pH 4. Because of this original negative charge in the superficial skin layers, it is relatively easy to introduce basic drugs (E.g. Methylene blue) through the skin. Electro osmosis, the transport of liquid water as a whole, can interfere with the mechanism of iontophoresis. This causes migration of undissociated molecules in solution. Because the skin has a negative charge, iontophoresis will effect movement of water in to the body from the positive pole iontophoretically towards the outer surface of the skin at the negative pole and cause swelling at the negative pole after intense iontophoresis. The process is helpful in case of cation transfer from the positive pole, as it acts in the same direction, facilitating absorption of the cationic drugs. Electro osmosis is highest in solutions with low conductivity.

4. Merits and Demerits (8)

A) Merits

1. It is a non-invasive technique could serve as a substitute for chemical enhancers.
2. It eliminates problems like toxicity problem, adverse reaction formulation problems associated with presence of chemical enhancers in pharmaceuticals.
3. It may permit lower quantities of drug compared to use in TDDS, this may lead to fewer side effects.
4. Iontophoresis prevent variation in the absorption of TDDS.
5. Eliminate the chance of over or under dosing by continuous delivery of drug programmed at the required therapeutic rate.
6. Provide simplified therapeutic regimen, leading to better compliance.
7. Permit a rapid termination of the modification, if needed, by simply by

stopping drug input from the iontophoretic delivery system.

8. Provide predictable and extended duration of action.
9. Reduce frequency of dosage.
10. Self-administration is possible.
11. It minimize inter and intra-patient variation.
12. An iontophoretic system also consists of a electronic control module which would allow for time varying of free-back controlled drug delivery.
13. Iontophoresis turned over control of local anesthesia delivery in reducing the pain of needle insertion for local anesthesia.
14. By minimizing the side effects, lowering the complexity of treatment and removing the need for a care to action.
15. Iontophoretic delivery prevents contamination of drugs reservoir for extended period of time.

B. Demerits

1. Iontophoretic delivery is limited clinically to those applications for which a brief drug delivery period is adequate.
2. An excessive current density usually results in pain.
3. Burns are caused by electrolyte changes within the tissues.
4. The safe current density varies with the size of electrodes.
5. The high current density and time of application would generate extreme pH, resulting in a chemical burn.
6. This change in pH may cause the sweat duct plugging perhaps precipitate protein in the ducts, themselves or cosmetically hyperhydrate the tissue surrounding the ducts.
7. Electric shocks may cause by high current density at the skin surface Possibility of cardiac arrest due to excessive current passing through heart.
8. Ionic form of drug in sufficient concentration is necessary for iontophoretic delivery.
9. High molecular weight 8000-12000 results in a very uncertain rate of delivery.

5. Factors Influencing the Iontophoresis

5.1. Effect of drug concentration ⁽⁹⁾

Drug concentration and its impact on iontophoretic flux is one of the most commonly studied experimental parameters and although the equations described above suggest the existence of a fairly straightforward correlation between the amount of

drug in the formulation and the observed flux, the experimental results demonstrate that frequently this is far from the case. These complications arise for a number of reasons: first, simply increasing the amount of drug in the formulation may not increase the number of molecules in the membrane; second, the concentrations and mobilities of competing ions play an important role; and third, due to the effect of drug physicochemical properties and their impact on the ability of the molecule to interact with structures along the iontophoretic transport pathway.

5.2. Effect of pH ⁽¹⁰⁾

The pH of the drug-containing solution in contact with the skin can impact on iontophoretic transport by two distinct mechanisms. It will obviously have an effect on the degree of ionization of the drug molecule for weak bases increasing pH will reduce the ionized fraction of the molecule and result in a decreased electromigratory contribution to iontophoretic transport.

5.3. Current Strength ⁽¹¹⁾

There is a linear relationship between the observed flux of a number of compounds and the applied current. With the present electrode area of 1 cm², the current is limited to 1 mA due to patient comfort considerations. This current should not be applied for more than three minutes because of local skin irritation and burns. With increasing current, the risk of non-specific vascular reactions (vasodilatations) increases. At a current of 0.4 to 0.5 mA/cm², such a vascular reaction is initiated after a few seconds of iontophoresis with deionised or tap water. This latter effect is probably due to the current density being high enough within a small area to stimulate the sensory nerve endings.

5.4. Ionic Competition ⁽¹²⁾

In a solution of sodium chloride, there is an equal quantity of negative (Cl⁻) and positive (Na⁺) ions Migration of a sodium ion requires that an ion of the opposite charge is in close vicinity. The latter ion of opposite charge is referred to as a counter-ion. An ion of equal charge but of a different type is referred to as a co-ion. When using iontophoresis, it is important to know that pH adjustment is performed by adding buffering agents. The use of buffering agents adds co-ions which are usually smaller and more mobile than the ion to be delivered. This results in a reduction of the number of drug ions to be delivered through the tissue barrier by the applied current.

5.5. Molecular Size ⁽¹³⁾

It has been shown that the permeability coefficients in positively charged, negatively charged and uncharged solutes across excised human skin are a function of molecular size. When the molecular size increases, the

permeability coefficient decreases. However, there are certain solutes with a relatively high molecular size (e.g. insulin, vasopressin and several growth hormones), which have also been shown to penetrate the skin barrier into the systemic circulation.

5.6. Physiological Factors⁽¹⁴⁾

Iontophoresis reduces intra- and inter-subject variability in the delivery rate. This is an inherent disadvantage with the passive absorption technique. Experiments *in vivo* and *in vitro* give support for clinical findings that there are small differences in the flux rate following transdermal iontophoresis between males and females, as well as between hairy and hairless skin. The status of the vascular bed is also important; for instance, a pre-constricted vascular bed decreases the drug flux through the skin while a dilated vascular bed increases the yield of the drug through the skin.

6. Optimising Iontophoretic Transport

1. Iontophoretic transport can be regulated by varying the applied current density and area of application. A current density that is too high may be unpleasant for the patient. If possible, avoid using current settings that result in more than 500 mA/cm. At high current densities there is a significant risk for unspecific electrically mediated vasodilatation that is not drug related.

2. The pH of the formulation should be optimised to ensure maximum ionisation of the compound. To prevent pH drifts during the iontophoresis, the choice of electrodes is of importance. With a correct electrode material, decreased solubility and precipitation of the compound are avoided.

3. Before iontophoresis is carried out, carefully clean the skin area to be used with deionised water or preferably 70 per cent alcohol. Cleaning will decrease the current needed and minimise the risk for local spots of high current density, which could result in C-fibre activation, vasodilatation and local micro-burns.

CONCLUSION:

Iontophoretic drug delivery systems form a major group of the relatively few physically enhanced transdermal delivery systems that have been successfully developed and commercialised. The electrically driven penetration enhancement provided by this method has succeeded in overcoming the formidable barrier presented by the SC, and has shown to be a promising technique for various agents, including macromolecules. Combination strategies with other physical enhancement

techniques such as electroporation or ultrasound or with chemical enhancers have led to the observation of significantly higher flux levels compared with passive transdermal delivery. However, the resulting irritation caused to the skin due to combined strategies may be a cause for concern. Also, electrically assisted delivery systems provide the advantage of controlled drug delivery with customised drug input rates, and an option of ceasing drug transport when desired. In addition, iontophoresis is also finding value in drug delivery via other drug administration routes such as transcorneal and trans-scleral routes, and also through bone for delivery of antibiotics to prevent infection during allograft implantation

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